

Pword-report

Language name: **Northern Qiang**
LID: 722 (for Qiang), **No separate LID for Northern and Southern Qiang! (should be made)**
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Sources: LaPolla, Randy J. with Chenglong Huang (2003). *A Grammar of Qiang. With annotated texts and glossary*. MGL 31. Berlin/NYC: Mouton de Gruyter.
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I Language profile

of spks: 57'300 (Northern Qiang only)
place: Aba Tibetan and Qiang Autonomous Prefecture, Sichuan Province, China (PR)
Contact lgs.: Mandarin, Tibetan
Status: not an official language
Prospects: endangered, parents are encouraging children to speak Mandarin, negative language attitude
Struct. results: borrowings mainly from Chinese, r-colouring is dropped by younger speakers

II Morpheme types

1. _____ Stem

2. _____ Restricted postposed formative

-(y)le 'PL' (with N only (and only with kinship terms, pronouns, and some nouns referring to people))

(1) *apə-le* 'grandfathers'

(2) *upu-le* 'uncles'

(3) *wutʂ^hu-pu-m-le-yle*
help-do-NMLZ-DEF-PL
'the helpers'

3. _____ Semi-restricted postposed formative

-*ni* 'ADV' (with A, V, N)

(4) *ɲuə-χua-ni*
COP-BECAUSE-ADV
'it is because ...'

(5) *fiə-tsəi-ni*
INT-this.manner-ADV
'in this way'

(6) *maha-ni*
night-ADV
'at night'

(7) *ɲi-χua-ni*
Q-BECAUSE-ADV
'why?'

(8) *a-dza-z-ni*
DIR-follow-CAUS-ADV
'following them'

(9) *de-ts^he-ni*
DIR-wrong-ADV
'wrongly'

4. _____ Semi-restricted preposed formative

mV- 'NEG' (with A, V) (the prefix undergoes vowel harmony)

(10) *mo-ku-χua-ni*
NEG-willing-BECAUSE-ADV
'deliberately'

(11) *ma-q fiə-mə-se*
NEG-go DIR-NEG-allow
'not to go would not be allowed = he must go'

(12) *ma-na*
NEG-good
'bad'

(13) *fiə-mə-tea-χtʂa*
DIR-NEG-CONTINUATIVE-small
'not so reduced'

N.B. All prefixes seem to be able to be attached to adjectives and verbs. But A and V are different POSs because only A can be used as attribute for Ns without marker.

→ 4 morpheme types

III Syllable

Syllable structure

The syllable canon is: (S)(C)(V)V(:/V)(^h)(S)(C) (S = fricative)

Possible syllable types:

(14)	V	a	'one'
(15)	VV	au	'one pile'
(16)	VC	as	'one day'
(17)	VCC	əχs	'tight'
(18)	CV	pə	'buy'
(19)	CVV	k ^h uə	'dog'
(20)	CVVV	kuai-t ^h a	'blame (vt.)'
(21)	CVC	paq	'interest'
(22)	CVCC	bəχs	'honey'
(23)	CVVC	duap	'thigh'
(24)	CCV	xtsɛ	'louse'
(25)	CCVV	skue	'roast'
(26)	CCVVV	skuəi	'mountain goat'
(27)	CCVC	spəl	'kidney'
(28)	CCVV	ɸnəi	'kind of wild goat'
(29)	CCVCC	spəχs	'Chibusu'
(30)	CCVVC	squap	'quiet'
(31)	CCVVCC	ɸpiex ^t	'scar'

Onset clusters (note some place assimilations and the voicing harmony within the clusters):

(32)	/sɸp/ → [ɸp] / ___i,e	spa	'sorghum'
		ɸpies	'noodle'
(33)	/sɸb/ → [zɸb] → [zɸ] / ___i	zɸbie	'soak (barley to make wine)'
		zɸbu	'drum'
(34)	/st/ → [st]	sta	'entrust to'
(35)	/sd/ → [zd]	zdu	'deer'
(36)	/sk/	skuə	'thief'
(37)	/sg/ → [zg]	zgue	'fox'
(38)	/sq/	squ	'boil'
(39)	/stɛ/ → [ɸtɛ]	ɸtɛ:mi	'heart'
(40)	/sdz/ → [zdz]	zdzɪ	'disease'
(41)	/sm/ → [zm]	zmu	'corpse'
(42)	/xk/	mi-xkam	'eyebrow'
(43)	/xts/	xtsu	'sweat'
(44)	/xdz/ → [ydz]	ydzə	'enough'
(45)	/xtɛ/	xtɛpi	'knife'
(46)	/xdz/ → [ydz]		no example given
(47)	/xs/	xsə	'new'
(48)	/xz/ → [ɸz]	ɸzə	'hot (peppery); numb'
(49)	/xɸ/	xɸu	'barking deer'
(50)	/xz/ → [ɸz]	ɸzɛm	'rice gruel, congee'
(51)	/xt/	x ^h tiex-buz ^h	'loess soil'
(52)	/xl/ → [ɸl]	ɸlu	'roll (v.)'
(53)	/χd/ → [ɸd]	ɸdua	'hammer (n.)'
(54)	/χq/	χqu	'gold'
(55)	/χs/	χsu	'living, to be alive'
(56)	/χz/ → [ɸz]	ɸzu	'chisel (n.)'
(57)	/χs/	χsə	'manure'
(58)	/χz/ → [ɸz]		no example given
(59)	/χts/	χtsu	'six'

(60)	/χdz/ → [ɬdz]	ɬdzəp	'toenail'
(61)	/χdz/ → [ɬdz]		no example given
(62)	/χt/	χtu	'hawk'
(63)	/χl/ → [ɬl]	ɬlu	'stone'
(64)	/χn/ → [ɬn]	ɬnəi	'kind of wild goat'
(65)	/χŋ/ → [ɬŋ]	ɬŋis	'spring (of water)'

Complex nuclei:

Vowel length is distinctive with all vowels except schwa (i:, y:, u:, e:, o:, a:, ɑ:), diphthongs and triphthongs occur, length is contrastive even with diphthongs and r-colored vowels. In native words the following diphthongs/triphthongs are possible: /ia, ia:, ia, ie, ya, ya:, ye, eu, əu, ei, əi, oi, ua, ua:, ua, ua:, uə, ue, ui, uəi/. (Maybe there are more long diphthongs, but no examples are given for them). Additionally, in Chinese loans occur /ai, au, uai, iau/. All vowels including the long vowels, long diphthongs can be r-coloured phonemically. (The "r-colouring" is a retroflex approximant after the vowel(s), which seems to belong to the nucleus, since it takes part in vowel harmony effects.)

Some examples:

(66)	/e:/	t ^h e:	'3s.PRON'
(67)	/eː/	k ^h eːχ	'comb'
(68)	/eː˥/	seː˥-muji	'mushroom'
(69)	/ə˥/	k ^h ə˥	'saw (vt.)'
(70)	/ye/	tɛye	'hoe (n.)'
(71)	/eu/	heu	'repay'
(72)	/ue/	gue-ŋi	'near'
(73)	/ue˥/	gue˥	'army'
(74)	/ue˥˥/	gue˥˥	'road'
(75)	/uəi/	skuəi	'mountain goat'
(76)	/iau/	p ^h iau-tsə	'paper money'

Complex codas:

The same clusters than in the onset are possible, with the same phonology.

Some examples:

(77)	/xɬ/	tɕ ^h exɬ	'sip (vt.)'
(78)	/xɕ/	wəxɕ	'horse dung'
(79)	/xz/ → [ɣz]	ləɣz	'book'
(80)	/xl/ → [ɣl]	əɣl	'upright'
(81)	/ɕtɛ/ → [ɕtɛ]	dzaɕtɛ	'laugh (v.)'
(82)	/xɕ/	laxɕ	'palm (of hand)'
(83)	/xtɕ/	əxtɕ	'shade (vt.)'

Monomoraic words

(84)	χqu	'gold'
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Vowel-initial words

(85)	əɣl	'upright'
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But optionally, a glottal stop is inserted to avoid vowel-initial words.

Polysyllabic morphemes

(86)	jimigu	'trace'
(87)	-ŋuəŋi	'TOP'

Phonotactics

- All consonant phonemes can be onsets, but /ŋ/ only before /u/. Thus syllables can not begin with /ŋa/ or /ŋi/ for instance.

(88)	ŋuə	'silver'
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As codas, the aspirated stops and affricates /p^h t^h k^h q^h ts^h tɕ^h/, the glottal fricatives /h fi/, and the palatal nasal /ɲ/ can not occur.

- (105) sə- 'DIR' + t^hə 'drink' → sətə 'drink.IMP'
 (106) ə- 'DIR' + dzua 'sit' → əzɥə 'sit.IMP'
 (107) ə- 'DIR' + dzə 'eat' → əz 'eat.IMP'
 (108) ma- 'NEG' + dzə 'able' → mal 'not able'
 (109) tə- 'DIR' + bə 'pile' → taw 'piled (perf.)'
 (110) tə- 'DIR' + ba 'big' → tawa 'become big'
 (111) a 'one' + tu 'span' → atɥ 'one handspan'

2. Vowel harmony

The vowel of the first syllable of a *prefix+stem* or *stem+stem* combination assimilates features of the vowel in the second syllable of that combination (schwa becomes a copy of the second vowel (except əhigh which does not seem to be predictable), /a a i/ sometimes take [əback, əround], r-colouring is also copied(!)):

- (112) wə 'bird' + ʃpu 'flock' → wuʃpu '(wild) pigeon'
 (113) ə- 'DIR' + pi 'uncle' → ipi 'uncle'
 (114) ə- 'DIR' + tse 'look at' → itse 'saw'
 (115) ha 'ten' + tʃi 'one' → hatʃi 'eleven'
 (116) ji 'two' + -su 'ten' → jusu 'twenty'
 (117) kua 'five' + k^he^t 'hundred' → kua^t-k^he^t 'five hundred'
 (118) me 'not' + we^t 'reduce' → me^t-we^t 'unceasingly'
 (119) a 'one' + tu 'span' → atɥ 'one handspan'
 but strangely:
 (120) a 'one' + guə 'basket' → agɥə 'one basketfull'

Sometimes the second part changes:

- (121) Chin. zhàogù + pə 'to do' → tʃauku-pu 'take care of'
 (122) Chin. wākǔ + pə 'to do' → kuak^hu-pu 'be sarcastic of'

3. Vowel epenthesis

To avoid disallowed consonant clusters (see Syllable section above), an epenthetic schwa is inserted. This rule especially applies to monosegmental suffixes like *-m*, *-n*, *-s*, *-ʃ*, *-z*.

- (123) niq 'black' + -ʃ 'TOO.MUCH' → niqəʃ 'too black'
 (124) zɔzi 'illness' + tʃ^hop 'cure' + -m 'AGT.NMLZ' → zɔzits^hopəm 'doctor'
 (125) bəl 'do' + -s 'INS.NMLZ' + je 'good to eat' → bələsje 'advantageous'
 (126) bəl 'do' + -z 'CAUS' + -mə 'NEG' + ku 'allow' → bələzmoɤu 'hinder'

4. Consonant assimilation

- 4a. /ʃ/ → [s] / ___t, d (within σ)
 4b. /ʃ/ → [ç] / ___pi, pe, bi, tɛ, dɛ (within σ)
 4c. [+cons] → [+voiced] / ___[+voiced, +cons] (within σ)

For examples cf. Syllable section above (examples (32) to (65)).

VI "Free" Grammatical Morphemes

A Prefix+Stem

Rules 1 to 3 apply, but prefixes do not always participate in stress assignment (cf. Section IV above). Stressed and unstressed prefixes can be mixed. Stressed syllables within one word can be adjacent (cf. (99)).

B Stem+Clitic

All "clitics" are phrasal suffixes (the case markers). They are treated as other suffixes and do not have separate stress or special rules applying.

VII Polymorphemic Stem forms

no mismatches found

VIII Compounds, Concatenations, Juxtapositions

Rules 1 to 3 apply to compounds. There are no direct examples for stress assignment in compounds, but since most words are monosyllabic, the weakening (rule 1) often forces a monosyllabic result of compounding or at least, the second vowel becomes unstressed. No rule applies across word boundaries.

IX Reduplication

Reduplication (sometimes with vowel ablaut in the first part) of verbs can have reciprocal (verbs with two human participants) or iterational (other verbs) meaning:

- | | | |
|-------|------------------|----------------------|
| (127) | <i>ku~ku</i> | 'curse each other' |
| (128) | <i>kuə~kuə</i> | 'help each other' |
| (129) | <i>sə~səː˩</i> | 'know each other' |
| (130) | <i>pʰiː~pʰiː</i> | 'tear each other' |
| (131) | <i>mə~mə</i> | 'be plastering' |
| (132) | <i>stui~stue</i> | 'be pulling (weeds)' |

Since the first reduplicant seems to undergo some reduction, it might be a kind of unstressed prefix (underlyingly /(_ωX)-/), but there are only indirect examples for stress assignment in reduplicated forms:

- | | | | | |
|-------|-------------------|----------------------------|----------------------------|-------------------------|
| (133) | <i>nə</i> - 'DIR' | + <i>lə~lə</i> 'exchange' | → <i>nəllə</i> 'exchanged' | (unstressed vowel loss) |
| (134) | <i>tə</i> - 'DIR' | + <i>tɕʰə~tɕʰə</i> 'weigh' | → <i>tətɕʰə</i> 'weighed' | (dito) |

X Phrase/Sentence-level phenomena

There are "no particular peaks on any one part of the clause" (LaPolla 2003, p. 33).

XI Other Special things

Geminates: There are geminates (even with affricates), but only with a syllable boundary in between. They appear to be not treated as single long segments, since all syllable-final rules (e.g. deaspiration as in (136)) apply to the first consonant.

- | | | |
|-------|-----------------|-------------|
| (135) | <i>tʰizzi</i> | '3d.PRON' |
| (136) | <i>tətɕʰɕʰə</i> | 'weighed' |
| (137) | <i>nəllə</i> | 'exchanged' |

Foot: The "normal" foot is trochaic, assigned from left. But stressed prefixes fall out of the "normal" foot structure, since they are always stressed, independent of their position within the word.